

Lunyu 論語, The Analects

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Entry tags: Canonical texts, Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Religious Group, Chinese Religion, Early Chinese text, Text, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

The Lunyu 論語, generally translated as The Analects, is a collection of sayings by or attributed to Confucius 孔子 (traditional dates 551–479 BCE), a ritual master who lived during the Eastern Zhou 東周 dynasty (770–221 BCE). These dialogues, often very brief and generic, were understood as indications on how to conduct oneself properly in society. A significant change that emerges from the Lunyu is the use of junzi 君子 (literally meaning “son of a lord”) to indicate a person who acts morally, regardless of birth (Goldin 2020: 49). This is tied to what seems a guiding principle in the Lunyu, in spite of its lack of a sustained argument. Many of the sayings attempt to establish a moral system that takes humans as yardstick, and leaves the veneration of spirits on the side. Some of the central virtues are humanity (ren 仁), morality (yi 義), and reciprocity (shu 恕). Yet, Confucius avoids giving any hard definition for any of these (Goldin 2020: 39, 41), for reasons unknown. Precisely because of the generic nature of these statements, a plethora of commentaries and interpretations has been and continues to be produced. ___ Confucius’ influence on the contemporaneous and following generations is attested primarily in two ways: one, his views are object of debate among other intellectuals. Most famously, Mozi 墨子 criticized ideas attributed to Confucius, while Mengzi 孟子 and Xunzi 荀子 included them in their own philosophical systems. Secondly, his sayings circulated across time and space, as archeological recoveries indicate: sections of the Lunyu dating to first century BCE have been recovered in modern North Korea at Pyongyang, in Dingzhou, China (both discussed in van Els 2018), and in what constituted the north-west frontier of the Han empire (Sanft 2019). ___ What we read today is based on a 17th century edition by Jin Pan 金蟠, based on the Lu 魯 Lunyu, one of the three major editions of this text mentioned by the Treatise on Arts and Letters 藝文志, the oldest extant bibliography included in the Book of Han 漢書. The other two versions are the Qi 齊 Lunyu, and the gu Lunyu 古論語, so named because it was written in ancient script, guwen 古文. According to the Shiji 史記, the guwen Lunyu was recovered in the wall of the once house of Confucius, when Prince Liu Yu 劉餘 (d. 127 BCE) demolished parts of it to expand it during the second century BCE. The Treatise further lists nine more textual lineages (jia 家) for this text, which are named after the scholars who taught them. It remains unclear if the differences rested in the content or the interpretations of these scholars. With the starting of the Han dynasty, the Qi and Lu Lunyu continued to circulate while others stopped being mentioned. ___ Although it was elevated to a classic only during the Tang 唐 dynasty (618–907), the Lunyu was already influential during the Han 漢 dynasty (206 BCE–220 CE). While of the Pyongyang Lunyu only a cursory study has been made available to scholars, studies on the Dingzhou Lunyu suggest that still by 50 BCE, the Lunyu was not a closed collection yet. ___ As of 2023, three manuscript discoveries that will cast more light on the textual history of the Analects have been announced. One is the scientifically excavated material from the tomb of the Marquis of Hai Hun 海昏後. This was the title taken by Liu He 劉賀 (?–59 BCE) after being deposed in 74 BCE. Initial publications on the Hai Hun texts describe 500 very poorly preserved strips of Lunyu material, including the chapter Zhi dao 知道. The Zhi dao is one of the two chapters (the other being the Wen wang 問王) that, according to Ban Gu 班固, characterized Qi Lunyu. However, the manuscript does not include the Wen wang, hence editors are reluctant to identify it as an exemplar of the Qi tradition. Furthermore, given the presence of other otherwise unattested chapters, they speculate on whether this may be a personal selection of chapters made by Liu He or his teacher. In support of this idea, the editors indicate that the material features of this manuscript suggest that the chapters were circulating independently, and that there is no reference to it as the Lunyu (the editors use the expression “Hai Hunhou Lunyu” as a matter of convenience, Zhu Fenghan 朱鳳瀚 2020). What this exactly entails for the textual history of the Lunyu remains open to debate, one that must await the publication of the Hai Hunhou corpus. ___ The two other

manuscripts are more revealing, because they date to the Warring States 戰國時代 (375–221BCE) era. They predate the moment of textual formation during the Western Han dynasty. One manuscript has been titled by the editors "Zhongni said" 仲尼曰. It is part of a group of looted manuscripts, purchased by the Anhui University in 2015. The second manuscript, "*Kongzi said" 孔子曰 is from the Wangjiazui 王家嘴 corpus, archaeologically excavated starting in 2019. Preliminary information published (see references below). As with the Anhui University manuscript, "*Kongzi said" 孔子曰 is a list of sayings attributed to Confucius. Some were known in the existing literature, others are otherwise unattested. While the Anda manuscript has been published in its entirety, the Wangjiazui one is still being curated.

Date Range: 500 BCE - 1911 CE

Region: Early and early imperial China

Region tags: Asia, China, East Asia

Core area of early and early imperial China

读者群情况：

✓ 非精英（普通人，普通民众）

来源和语料库

纸质来源

用于理解此课题的纸质信息来源

– Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions.

– Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998.

– Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008

Notes: Other recent translations in English languages include: Edward Slingerland, tr. *Confucius: Analects, with Selections from Traditional Commentaries*. Indianapolis and Cambridge, Mass.: Hackett, 2003; Moss Roberts, tr. *The Analects: Conclusions and Conversations of Confucius*. Oakland: University of California Press, 2020. For Italian, see Tiziana Lippiello, tr. *Confucio: Dialoghi*. Torino: Einaudi, 2003.

Reference: 武内義雄, Takeuchi Yoshio. *Rongo No Kenkyū 論語の研究*. Tokyo: Iwanami, 1939.

Reference: Tetsuji 諸橋轍次, Morohashi. *Rongo No Kōgi 論語の講義*. Tokyo, 1939.

Reference: Goldin, Paul R.. *Confucianism*. London: Routledge, 2011.

Reference: Goldin, Paul R., ed.. *A Concise Companion to Confucius*. Edited by Paul R. Goldin. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2017.

Reference: Zhu Fenghan . “海昏竹簡《論語》初論 (preliminary Discussion of the Lunyu from Hai Hun Tomb)”. In *Hai Hun Jian Du Chu Lun 海昏簡牘初論 (preliminary Discussion of the Strips and Tables from Hai Hun Tomb)*, 154–80. Beijing: Beijing Daxue Chubanshe 北京大學出版社, 2020.

Reference: Hunter, Michael. *Confucius Beyond the Analects*. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2017.

Reference: Hunter, Michael, and Martin Kern. *Confucius and the Analects Revisited: New Perspectives on Composition, Dating, and Authorship*. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2018.

Reference: van Els, Paul. “Confucius’s Sayings Entombed: On Two Han Dynasty Bamboo Lunyu

Manuscripts". In *Confucius and the Analects Revisited: New Perspectives on Composition, Dating, and Authorship*, 152–86. Leiden: Brill, 2018.

Reference: State Bureau of Cultural Relics (China). "Dingxian 40 Hao Han Mu Chutu Zhujian Jianjie 定2縣40號漢墓出土竹簡簡介". *Wenwu 文物 Cultural Relics*, 1981.

Reference: Slingerland, Edward. *Confucius Analects: With Selections from Traditional Commentaries*. Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing, 2003.

Reference: Sanft, Charles. "Questions About the Qi Lunyu". *T'oung Pao*, 2018.

Reference: Hunter, Michael. "Did Mencius Know the Analects?". *T'oung Pao*, 2014.

Reference: Cheng Shude, 程樹德, ed.. *Lunyu Jiishi 論語集釋*. Edited by 程樹德 Cheng Shude. Beijing : Zhonghua shuju 中華書局, 1990.

在线信息来源

用于理解此课题的在线信息来源

– Source 1 URL: CText 中國哲學書電子化計劃 <https://ctext.org/analects/zh>

– Source 1 Description: Scripta Sinica 漢籍電子文獻資料庫, <http://hanchi.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/ihp/hanji.htm>

– Source 2 URL: Database of Chinese Classics 中華經典古籍庫, <http://publish.ancientbooks.cn/docShuju/platformSublibIndex.jsp?libId=6>

在线语料库

相关在线一手文献语料库 (原文以及/或者译文)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/confucianism/zh>

– Source 1 Description: CText Confucian corpus

– Source 2 URL: [http://hanchi.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/ihpc/hanjiquery?
@26^513667392^802^^^30101001@@206011738#top](http://hanchi.ihp.sinica.edu.tw/ihpc/hanjiquery?@26^513667392^802^^^30101001@@206011738#top)

– Source 2 Description: Scripta Sinica, corpus of the Thirteenth Classics

一般变量 (General Variables)

物质性 (Materiality)

创作方式

– Written

Notes: Oral teaching coexisted at the same time.

↳ 油墨制 (inked)

– with Ink

Notes: The Lunyu 論語 most certainly collects sayings by Confucius and his disciples, written down during the first centuries BCE.

书写/雕刻文字的媒介

– Bamboo

Notes: During the Warring States era, the main medium for textual sources was bamboo; possibly some chapters of the Lunyu may have been written on silk too. Chapters seem to have circulated independently, until a process of collation during the Han dynasty gave this collection of sayings the form we see today.

– Paper

请具体说明纸的类型

– Specify: Starting with the Tang dynasty, paper becomes a major support for writing and reproducing texts. The woodcock printing technique was replaced by the movable type technique in the 11th century CE.

在书写和雕刻之前，材料是否被修改过？

– Physical preparation

Notes: Bamboo was cut into strips of uniform size. (See review of studies on the subject in Xiao 2017: 235-46.)

Reference: Xiao, Yunxiao. “Restoring Bamboo Scrolls: Observations on the Materiality of Warring States Bamboo Manuscripts”. *Chinese Studies in History* 50 (2017): 235-54.

在书写和雕刻之前，文本是否被修改过？

– Other [specify]: Field does not know the extent to which the sayings were modified.

地点

文本是否存放于明确的场所？

【注明时间点，供参考（如果知道）；选择所有适用答案。】

– No

Notes: Other than copies in the Imperial Library. Some copies (e.g. Hai Hunhou) appear to have been stored in tombs.

存放文字的位置是否伴有标记或者图像？

– No

存放文字的区域是否有标志性的图像？

– No

生产和目标受众

生产

文本生产是否由政体资助？

– No

文本是否被认为是官方的宗教经文？

– 否

Notes: Confucius will be given a status similar to that of a saint during the Han dynasty, and The Analects are attached an aura of marked reverence. However, it remains in my opinion not a scripture, since its compilation is not sacred in any sense (i.e., connected with a god, dictated by one, or written in a sacred language).

用特定的宗教/神圣的语言书写？

– No

目标受众

估计有多少人被认为是文本的受众？

这应该是作为文本预期受众的总人数。

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Potentially, everybody.

宗教团体积极劝人信教、招募新成员吗？

– No

是否有明确的改革派活动？

(改革派，比如不是奉劝新保守主义者改教，而是“转化”，或者说改良相关教义，使其变成“正确的阐释”？)

– No

本文本是否用于仪式活动？

– No

物品对于文本来说重要吗？

– No

文本的语境和内容（信仰和实践）。

上下文语境

是否有艺术伴随文本出现？

– No

有多个文本版本吗？

– Yes

Notes: The Yi wen zhi 藝文志, the oldest extant bibliography included in the Book of Han 漢書, records three editions of the Lunyu: a Gu 古《論語》, a Qi 齊《論語》, and a Lu 魯《論語》. The Gu and Qi editions were lost during the Sui 隨 dynasty. A most recent recovery from the Hai Hun tomb has brought to light an edition somewhat close to the Qi Analects, although not entirely (see introduction and Zhu Fenghan 2020).

↳ 有多个正确版本吗？

– No

Notes: Once the text was canonized in the Han dynasty, it seems to have been transmitted in a daily stable way. Prior to that, we know that different editions existed, but these differed (according to what we can reconstruct) in the sequence and number of chapters, and graphic variants. There is no indication that one was more proper than another.

↳ 是否有关于哪个版本是正确的争论？

– No

文本是否在为一系列文本的一部分？

– No

Notes: It became eventually one of the classics that formed the core of Chinese literati education for centuries.

如果文本不是明确的经文，它是否属于另一个重要的文学传统？

– Yes

Notes: It became part of the Chinese Classics during the Tang dynasty.

↳ 具有宗教意义的文化

– Yes

Notes: The Confucian (also Ru 儒) tradition had and continues to have strong cultural implications in East Asia. Whether or not it has religious implications depends on the definition of "religion" one subscribes to.

↳ 行为学文献 (Behavioral literature)

– No

↳ 其他

– Other [specify]: The Lunyu is often referred to as one of the masters' texts, i.e. texts identified with masters that lived in pre-imperial times, such as Mengcius, Xunaiz, Han Feizi, etc., and are traditionally identified as the authors of the philosophical texts named after them.

内容

此文本是否就是或者包含仪式清单、手册、书目、索引、或者词汇表？（选择所有适用选项）

– Vocabulary

Notes: Philosophers who identified themselves as followers of Confucius' continued to use the vocabulary in use in the Analects (e.g., the use of "junzi" to indicate a moral person).

是否有复数世系或者单个世系由文本建立？

– No

Notes: Mencius and Xunzi, two thinkers who lived after Confucius, most likely identified themselves as his followers. Later traditions draw a direct line from Confucius to Mencius and Xunzi. (See Goldin 2020 chapters four and five.)

文本是否表达了一个正式的法律规定？

– No

制订专门的宗教历法？

– No

信仰

文本中是否存在灵与肉的区别？

– No

文本中是否表明相信有死后生命？

– 否

Notes: With the exception of Lunyu 7.21, "The subjects on which the Master did not talk, were: extraordinary things, feats of strength, disorder, and spiritual beings, 子不語怪，力，亂，神。" (James Legge's translation). The exact nature of Shen 神 "supernatural being" is however not specified further. Similarly, "spirits" 鬼神 are referred to in 6.22, 8.21, 11.12. Yet, it is unclear what spirits these are, and whether they do in fact reside in something that could be defined as "afterlife."

文本中是否注明相信这个世界有轮回？

– No

文中是否提到对信徒的尸体进行特殊处理？

– No

文本是否指出应该在埋葬时出现共同献祭？

– No

文本是否指明用于埋葬的墓葬品？

– No

文本中是否存在正式的埋葬？

– Yes

Notes: They are present only as references to an existing burial system. The Analects does not discuss it directly, nor present a new one.

↳ 作为墓碑？

– No

↳ 在基地里？

– Yes

↳ 家族地下墓室 (Family tomb-crypt) ？

– Yes

↳ 家里 (个人被埋在房子下面，或用于正常家庭活动的地方)

– No

↳ 其他正式埋葬类型？

– No

↳ 其他密集的丧葬仪式

– Specify: Not specified.

文本中是否展现了与葬礼有关的实践？

– No

文本中是否有超自然生物存在？

– Yes

Notes: Ghosts and spirits (鬼神) are referred to, but not directly discussed.

↳ 是否有至上天神存在？

— 否

Notes: Heaven 天 in the Analects is described variously: it is an entity that must not be offended (Lunyu 3.13), is considered to be the source of virtue (de 德, Lunyu 7.23), and bestowing richness and honors (Lunyu 12.5). If by "high-god" is meant an anthropomorphic omniscient entity that tests humans in life and judges them after their death, then Heaven in the Analects does not respond to this description. Given how lapidary (and at times obscure) some of the changes collected in the Analects are, it is also difficult to articulate a concept of Heaven sustained throughout the text.

先前人类灵魂存在

— No

Notes: Spirits (shen 神, gui 鬼) are to be sacrificed to, and must be revered. These can be spirits of ancestors or of mountains and river. There is no direct indication that these spirits are present.

非人类超自然生灵是存在的

— Yes

Notes: Spirits (shen 神, gui 鬼) are to be sacrificed to, and must be revered. These can be spirits of ancestors or of mountains and river. There is no direct indication that these spirits are present.

↳ 超自然存在可以被看见

— I don't know

Notes: Text does not specify

↳ 超自然存在可以被物理感知

— I don't know

Notes: Text does not specify

↳ 非人类超自然存在对这个世界有认知

— No

↳ 非人类超自然存在在这个世界有蓄意的因果效应

— No

↳ 根据文本，非人类自然存在是否可以与生灵沟通？

— No

↳ 这些超自然存在在世界有间接因果效应

— No

↳ 这些超自然存在展现积极的情绪

– No

↳ 这些超自然存在展现负面情绪

– No

↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感

– No

↳ 这些超自然存在具有/展现一些其他特点

– Specify: None

文本是否证明了一个超自然存在的神系 (pantheon) ?

– No

根据文本，人神混合的生灵是否存在？

– No

是否有一个超自然的存在，在文本中实际存在/作为文本的结果？

– No

是否有其他类别的生命存在？

– Mysterious?

Notes: See Lunyu 7.21 discussed above.

文本是否指导占卜实践？

– No

超自然监视

文本中是否有超自然监视？

– No

在文本中，超自然存在是否会施以惩罚

– No

在文本中，超自然的生命是否赋予了奖赏？

– No

救世主义/末世论

文本中是否存在救世主信仰？

– No

文本中是否存在末世论？

– No

规范与道德现实主义

一般的社会规范是由文本规定的吗？

– Yes

在宗教文本中是否有习俗惯例与道德的区别？

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the introduction, Confucius re-defines some norms on the basis of moral standards rather than birth-based rights. But The Analects is also famously vague in its definitions.

↳ 这种区别的本质是什么

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ 具体的道德规范是由文本规定的吗？

– Yes

Notes: There is a clear emphasis on norms such as reciprocity, morality, humanity; but the Analects famously does not provide detailed definitions of these.

↳ 具体而言，道德规范与模糊的形而上学概念隐含着联系

– No

↳ 口头规范与模糊的形而上学实体有明确的联系

– No

↳ 与非个人的宇宙秩序相联系（例如，因果报应）。

– No

↳ 以某种方式与一个拟人化的存在相联系

– No

↳ 具体来说，道德规范与拟人化的存在的命令有明确的联系

– No

↳ 具体而言，道德规范与形而上学没有特殊联系。

– No

↳ 道德规范适用于（选择所有适用的选项）。

– All individuals (any time period)

文本中是否有核心的重要美德主张？

– 是

Notes: As a general description, a "noble person" 君子 is one who responds morally in every and each situation. What is the best moral response however is not always given in the text, and Confucius indicates also that individuals must think by themselves what is moral.

↳ 诚实/守信/正直

– No

↳ 勇气（在战斗中）

– No

↳ 勇气（总体上的）

– No

↳ 怜悯/同情/仁慈/善意

– Yes

Notes: According to Analects 6.23, "The Master said, "The wise find pleasure in water; the virtuous find pleasure in hills. The wise are active; the virtuous are tranquil. The wise are joyful; the virtuous are long-lived, 子曰：「知者樂水，仁者樂山；知者動，仁者靜；知者樂，仁者壽。(James Legge's translation.) "Humanity" (仁, also translated as "benevolence") is more important than wisdom. See Goldin 2020: 40-41.

↳ 怜悯/宽恕/宽容

– No

↳ 慷慨/慈善

– No

↳ 无私/无私奉献

– No

↳ 正义/道德正直

– Yes

↳ 仪式的纯洁性/对仪式的坚持/对不洁来源的戒断

– Yes

↳ 尊重/礼让

– No

↳ 家庭顺从/孝顺

– Yes

Notes: "Filiality", xiao 孝, recurs in the Analects. Family has a privileged place in the process of moral growth of the individual.

↳ 忠心/忠诚

– No

↳ 合作

– Yes

↳ 独立性/创造性/自由

– No

↳ 节制/节俭

– No

↳ 忍耐/宽容/忍耐

– No

↳ 勤奋/自律/卓越

– No

↳ 勇气/决断力/信心/主动性
- No

↳ 力量 (生理的)
- No

↳ 权力/地位/贵族身份
- No

↳ 谦逊/谦虚
- No

↳ 知足常乐/宁静/心平气和
- No

↳ 喜悦/热情/欢快的心情
- No

↳ 乐观主义/希望
- No

↳ 感恩/感激之情
- No

↳ 尊敬/敬畏/惊奇
- Yes

↳ 信仰/信念/信任/奉献
- No

↳ 智慧/理解
- Yes

↳ 洞察力/智力
- Yes

↳ 美貌/吸引力

– No

↳ 洁净（生理的）/秩序

– No

↳ 其他重要的美德

– No

时间的倡导

圣经是否要求独身主义（完全禁欲）？

– No

文本是否要求对性活动进行限制（部分禁欲）？

– No

该文本是否要求阉割？

– No

文本要求禁食吗？

– No

文本是否要求放弃食物机会（对渴望的食物的禁忌）？

– No

该文本是否要求永久的伤疤或痛苦的身体改变？

– No

文本是否要求痛苦的身体姿势或短暂的痛苦伤口？

– No

文本是否要求成人献祭？

– No

文本是否要求儿童献祭？

– No

该文本是否要求自我献祭（自杀）？

– No

文本是否要求献祭财产/贵重物品

– No

文本是否要求牺牲时间（例：参加会议或服务，定期祈祷等）。

– No

该文本是否需要承担生理风险？

– No

该文本是否要求接受道德戒律？

– Yes

该文本是否要求群体外成员的边缘化

– No

文本是否要求参与小规模仪式（私人、家庭）？

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifices to parents and ancestors are fundamental for all families, and it is conceivable that some of these rituals happened privately.

演出的平均间隔时间是多少？

– Field doesn't know

文本是否要求参加大型仪式？

– I don't know

文中是否指出团体内部额外的仪式标记

– No

文本是否使用了拟亲属关系用语？

– No

文本中是否包括旨在娱乐的元素？

– No

文本中是否规定了祭品、供品和圣地的维护？

– Yes

↳ 文本是否规定献祭？

– Yes

Notes: There are references to sacrifices to parents; to spirits; and to ghosts; the term "great sacrifice" (大祭) is also used; sacrificial meat is mentioned twice. However, none of these is described in detailed, nor theorized upon.

↳ 动物献祭？

– Yes

Notes: A reference is in Analects 3.17: "Zi Gong wished to do away with the offering of a sheep connected with the inauguration of the first day of each month. The Master said, "Ci, you love the sheep; I love the ceremony, 子貢欲去告朔之餼羊。子曰：「賜也，爾愛其羊，我愛其禮。」 (James Legge's translation.) This has been considered a sign that by Confucius's times, there was a change in the way rituals were perceived. See references attached.

Reference: Milbourn, Oliva. "Confucius and His Dog: Perspectives on Animal Ownership in Early Chinese Ritual and Philosophical Texts". 漢學研究第 29 卷第, no. 4 期 (2011): 289-315. http://ccsdb.ncl.edu.tw/ccs/image/01_029_004_01_10.pdf.

Reference: Tavor, Ori. "Religious Thought". In *Routledge Handbook of Early Chinese History*, 261-79. Boca Raton, FL: Taylor & Francis, an imprint of Routledge, 2018.

↳ 人类献祭？

– No

↳ 文本是否规定自我献祭？

– No

Notes: There are some references to the kind of sacrifice. E.g., sacrifice to one's parents, Lunyu 2.5; the "grand sacrifice" 禘 is mentioned in Lunyu 3.10; sacrificial meat is also mentioned in Lunyu 10.15.

↳ 有物质祭品出现吗？

– No

↳ 是否必须参加崇拜/献祭？

– Yes

Notes: The answer relates to the overall idea in the text that filial piety is central to moral growth, and filial piety includes sacrificing correctly to one's family. While the text never specifies attendance as mandatory, it is plausible that it was so conceived.

↳ 由社群规定？
– I don't know

↳ 由特定个人规定？
– No

↳ 场所的维护是否由文本规定？
– No

文本的机构和生产环境

社会与机构

生产文本的宗教团体的社会，最适合被描绘为：

– A state

Notes: Hierarchical society, where education is part of a privileged section of it (all men, as far as we know). Social mobility is present, albeit limited.

是否有社会的特定因素控制了文本的再生产（reproduction）？

– Other

Notes: Transmission among people who accessed Confucius' teachings.

是否有特定的社会元素参与到文本的破坏中？

– Other

Notes: The regular losses of material happening during wars or dynastic changes; the act of standardization and canonization of the text that eliminated other circulating editions.

福利

文本中是否规定了制度化的饥荒救济？

– No

文本中是否规定了制度化的扶贫？

– No

文本中是否规定了对老弱病残的机构护理？

– No

其他形式的福利

– No

教育

是否有正式的教育机构可用于教授该文本？

– Yes

Notes: Starting with the Han empire we have references of educational centers; the capital itself has an imperial library that collects exiting literature. This was certainly true of the Qin empire, although little is known about it; most likely, similar institutions existed during the Zhou dynasty as well.

根据文本，是否有规定的正式教育机构？

– No

文本是否对非宗教教育作出规定？

– No

文本是否限制了宗教专业人士接受的教育？

– No

文本是否限制了宗教专业人士间的教育？

– No

根据文本，教育是否有性别差异？

– No

Notes: Except that, because of social practices, education remained for centuries primarily a male privilege.

就这个文本和更大的文本传统而言，教育是否具有性别差异？

– Yes

Notes: Although the moral principles are open to anyone, the society at the time seem to have given access to education only to men.

文本中是否规定了教学关系或比例？(即：1:20；1:1)

– No

文本是否有倡导与教师的具体关系？

– No

Notes: While the text never directly addresses this, some aspects can be inferred from the nature of the exchanges between Confucius and his disciples. Teachers are meant as guidance and yet they do not give direct answers; rather, they want their interlocutors to think by themselves what the answer may be. See also studies by Paul Goldin in bibliography.

根据文本本身的规定，教育是否有世俗的报偿/好处？

– No

官僚机构

官僚机构是由这个文本规范的吗？

– No

Notes: Although the text was read as bearing on the structure of society and government. There is no direct discussion however of bureaucratic systems.

公共工程

文本是否详细说明了与公共服务、设施 (public works) 的互动？

– No

税收

文本是否规定了征税的形式？

– No

战争

文本是否提到战争？

– Yes

Notes: War (zhan 戰) is referred once as something to be extremely cautious about.

↳ 文本是否规定了如何控制一个制度化的军队？

– No

↳ 文本是否限制/倡导参加外部的军事组织？

– No

↳ 文中是否庆祝/不满外源性军事力量的保护/征服？

– No

食物生产

文本中是否提到粮食生产/发放？

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Zhao Xiaobin, 趙曉斌. “湖北荊州王家嘴M798出土戰國楚簡《孔子曰》概述”. Jiang Han Kaogu 江漢考古 2, no. 185 (2023): 43-48.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Allan, Sarah. “Not the Lun Yu: The Chu Script Bamboo Slip Manuscript, Zigao, and the Nature of Early Confucianism”. Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London 72, no. 1 (2009): 115-51.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Slingerland, Edward. Confucius Analects: With Selections from Traditional Commentaries. Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing, 2003.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Csikszentmihalyi, Mark, and Tae-Hyun Kim. “With “the Formation of the Analects” ,pp. 152-165”. In Confucius: The Analects. Michael Nylan, Ed.. New York: W. W. Norton, 2014.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Huang Dekuan, 黃德寬. “Anhui Daxue Cang Zhanguo Zhujian Gaishu 安徽大學藏戰國竹簡概述”. Wenwu 文物 9 (2017): 54-59.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Zhu Fenghan, 朱鳳瀚. ““xihan Haihunhou Liu He Mu Chutu Zhujian Shi Chutan” 西漢海昏侯劉賀墓出土竹簡《詩》初探 (an Interpretation of the Bamboo Slips with the Content of the Book of Poetry Unearthed from the Tomb of Liu He, Marquis Haihun of the Western Han Dynasty)”. Cultural Relics 6 (2020): 63-72.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Zhu Fenghan. “海昏竹簡《論語》初論 (preliminary Discussion of the Lunyu from Hai Hun Tomb)”. In Hai Hun Jian Du Chu Lun 海昏簡牘初論 (preliminary Discussion of the Strips and Tables from Hai Hun Tomb), 154-80. Beijing: Beijing Daxue Chubanshe 北京大學出版社, 2020.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Zhu Fenghan, 朱鳳瀚, ed.. Haihun Jian Du Chulun 海昏簡牘初論. Edited by 朱鳳瀚 Zhu Fenghan. Beijing: Beijing daxue chubanshe, 2020.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Huang Dekuan, 黃德寬, and 徐在国 Xu Zaiguo, eds.. 安徽大學藏戰國竹簡 (二) anhui Daxue Cang Zhanguo Zhujian (er). Edited by 黃德寬 Huang Dekuan and 徐在国 Xu Zaiguo. Shanghai: Zhonghua Shuju 中華書局, 2022.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Jia Lianxiang, 賈連翔. “明體與釋讀:安大簡《仲尼曰》附記類文字綜論”. In 戰國文字研究青年學者論壇論文集, 2022.

Reference: Lunyu 論語, The Analects, Gu Shikao, 顧史考 (Scott Cook). “Anda Zhanguo Zhujian “zhongni Yue” Chutan 安大戰國竹簡《仲尼曰》初探”. 第三十四屆中國文字學國際學術研討會論文集, 2023.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, 武內義雄, Takeuchi Yoshio. *Rongo No Kenkyū 論語の研究*. Tokyo: Iwanami, 1939.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Tetsuji 諸橋轍次, Morohashi. *Rongo No Kōgi 論語の講義*. Tokyo, 1939.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Goldin, Paul R.. *Confucianism*. London: Routledge, 2011.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Goldin, Paul R., ed.. *A Concise Companion to Confucius*. Edited by Paul R. Goldin. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, 2017.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Zhu Fenghan . “海昏竹簡《論語》初論 (preliminary Discussion of the Lunyu from Hai Hun Tomb)”. In *Hai Hun Jian Du Chu Lun 海昏簡牘初論 (preliminary Discussion of the Strips and Tables from Hai Hun Tomb)*, 154–80. Beijing: Beijing Daxue Chubanshe 北京大學出版社, 2020.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Hunter, Michael. *Confucius Beyond the Analects*. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2017.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Hunter, Michael, and Martin Kern. *Confucius and the Analects Revisited: New Perspectives on Composition, Dating, and Authorship*. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2018.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, van Els, Paul. “Confucius’s Sayings Entombed: On Two Han Dynasty Bamboo Lunyu Manuscripts”. In *Confucius and the Analects Revisited: New Perspectives on Composition, Dating, and Authorship*, 152–86. Leiden: Brill, 2018.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, State Bureau of Cultural Relics (China). “Dingxian 40 Hao Han Mu Chutu Zhujian Jianjie 定2縣40號漢墓出土竹簡簡介”. *Wenwu 文物 Cultural Relics*, 1981.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Slingerland, Edward. *Confucius Analects: With Selections from Traditional Commentaries*. Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing, 2003.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Sanft, Charles. "Questions About the Qi Lunyu". *T'oung Pao*, 2018.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Hunter, Michael. "Did Mencius Know the Analects?". *T'oung Pao*, 2014.

Reference: Physical preparation, Xiao, Yunxiao. "Restoring Bamboo Scrolls: Observations on the Materiality of Warring States Bamboo Manuscripts". *Chinese Studies in History* 50 (2017): 235-54.

Reference: Yes, Milbourn, Oliva. "Confucius and His Dog: Perspectives on Animal Ownership in Early Chinese Ritual and Philosophical Texts". *漢學研究*第 29 卷第, no. 4 期 (2011): 289-315.
http://ccsdb.ncl.edu.tw/ccs/image/01_029_004_01_10.pdf.

Reference: Yes, Tavor, Ori. "Religious Thought". In *Routledge Handbook of Early Chinese History*, 261-79. Boca Raton, FL: Taylor & Francis, an imprint of Routledge, 2018.

Reference: Source 1: Lunyu Zhu Shu 論語注疏. Various editions., Source 2: E. Bruce and A. Taeko Brooks, trs. *The Original Analects: Sayings of Confucius and His Successors*. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998., Source 3: HUANG Huai-hsin 黃懷信 et al. *Lun-yü hui-chiao chi-shih 論語彙校集釋*. 2 vols. Chung-hua yao-chi chi-shih ts'ung-shu. Shanghai, 2008, Cheng Shude, 程樹德, ed.. *Lunyu Jiishi 論語集釋*. Edited by 程樹德 Cheng Shude. Beijing : Zhonghua shuju 中華書局, 1990.